

A Study of AIDS Awareness among Adult's Slum from the Areas of Agra

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Abstract

The present study aims at the investigation of AIDS awareness among adult's slum from the areas of Agra. The sample considered 100 male and 100 female adults from various slum's of Agra. The adults were selected on the simple random sample method. Self constructed questionnaire were used for the investigation of AIDS awareness.

At all levels of Indian human culture, instruction in matter of sex and relation has been closely bound up with the social mores and the prevailing codes of ethics applied to sex conduct and in development of these codes, religion has been a dominant factor. Generally, youngsters use different strategies to satisfy their curiosities and queries about sex. Considering all these facts in the mind, the present study was carried out to know awareness among adults of slum areas in Agra regarding AIDS disease.

Introduction

The main causes of death among young adults in most European and African countries are AIDS, drug over dose, suicide and traffic accidents. All these causes are related with life styles and risk behaviors and therefore, avoidable. Acquire Immune-Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is an illness caused by virus which destroys the immunity system of the body. Blood works as a defence system to save from the unwanted invaders, which harms the normal function of the body.

AIDS is a silent killer. The main reason for AIDS (Acquired Immuno Deficiency Syndrome) is HIV (Human Immuno Deficiency virus). This virus when it enters our body, immediately turns into RNA, and then spreads quickly. After that it starts to destroy the white blood corpuscles. Because of this our resistance towards diseases gets decreased. At this stage, the human body cannot withstand even an ordinary cold. The Human Immuno-deficiency Virus (HIV) is transmitted through blood transfusion. AIDS can be called our modern pandemic affecting both industrialized and developing countries.

In India, the first case of HIV was diagnosed in 1985 by National Institute of Virology. Since then sero surveys all over the country, have shown sero positivity among the high risk groups i.e., commercial sex workers and professional blood donors. The north-eastern states have shown a very high increase of sero positivity due to increase in the injecting drug users. It is estimated that at least 80 percent of all new cases of HIV infection are acquired heterosexually. Changing sexual behaviour through health education would thus have a significant impact on the further spread of AIDS.

Amongst 1.25 billion residents of India, around 2.4 million are presently suffering from Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). As per the Aids Report 2011 published by the United Nations, new HIV infectivity in India has declined at the rate of 50 % during the past 10 years. People suffering from HIV AIDS cases are mostly found in the southern and north-eastern part of India. In the present scenario Acquired Immune Deficiency syndrome (AIDS) has become one of the most serious mother epidemic which has spread to every continent and even to most remote areas of the earth. It is a ticking time bomb and none knows as to when it will throw as headlong into the abyss. The official estimate of HIV cases in India is 5.1 million, but the Executive Director of the Global Fund fears that this could be a gross under reporting.

Today's youth and adults are going to build tomorrow's future. They build the nation and they together build the world. Each one has his/her own responsibility in building a healthy world. Because of the scientific invention many diseases are eradicated many can be cured but still there are certain exceptions like HIV/AIDS virus which threatens the whole world. At first, youth and adults must realize the present problem created by HIV virus and their self control is going to be the main solution to the problem. HIV prevalence rate in our country vary from state to state.

Although, district Agra of Uttar Pradesh State is primarily an urban area, it has about 200 slums having a population of about 500,000. The reproductive health status of women living in these slums

is very poor. A coverage evaluation of maternal care, organized by UNICEF in 1998- 99 reported low achievement of various maternal care indicators. Coverage of Tetanus Toxoid Injection among antenatal mothers was reported to be 37.5%, consumption of Iron Folate tablets as 5.4%. About 58% of total deliveries are conducted at home out of which, 38% are conducted by untrained persons {Untrained traditional birth attendants (TBAs) and family members}, post natal care was also very poor. The average age at marriage of women were found to be as low as 16.8 years. In another study conducted jointly by WHO-NACO (National AIDS Control Organization, Government of India) and S.N. Medical College, Agra, a point prevalence of about 35.2% of RTIs (Reproductive Tract Infections) / STDs (Sexually Transmitted Disease) among women of reproductive age group was observed. This study on health seeking behavior of women with STDs revealed that out of those affected, 52% didn't seek any medical advice as they thought of it to be normal phenomena during reproductive age. Only 5% of the women accepted that the illness was sexually transmitted.

AIDS awareness and Sex-education would help male and female to develop positive attitude towards sex when their queries are satisfied honestly and scientifically. Young have so many myths about their organic development systems, body changes, hormonal effects on reproductive system, chronological maturity and its physiological impacts, when they become anxious, stressful and over-pressurized, nobody is their to help, guide and to explain different facts of male-female relationship to cope with her / his felt sexual urges. AIDS awareness focuses largely though not exclusively, on the individual, self awareness, personal relationship, human sexual development, reproduction & sexual behaviour. Human sexuality is the core of young education. It is a function of total personality, which includes the human reproductive system and processes, attitude towards being a male or a female.

AIDS Awareness

HIV and AIDS are very closely related. AIDS stands for Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome, a disease in which the body's immune system breaks down. AIDS is caused by a virus called the "human immunodeficiency virus," more commonly referred to as HIV. The HIV virus may live in the body for years before it is even noticed until symptoms begin appearing. It is important to note that although there are no visible symptoms, the virus can still be transmitted. Actually a person can go without having symptoms for up to 10-15 years. An HIV / AIDS awareness program will tell you

all about this dreaded pandemic. No other word engenders as much fear, revulsion, despair and utter helplessness as AIDS. Despite increased HIV / AIDS awareness, the terror persists. AIDS is, in fact, rewriting medical history as humankind's deadliest scourge.

Slum Area

Defining an area as a slum area is very complex task since there is no any authentic definition or documentation exists in the country for defining slum. A simple definition of a slum would be “a heavily populated urban area characterized by substandard housing and squalor”.

Objective of the Study

1. To study the AIDS awareness of Adult male of slum areas in Agra.
2. To study the AIDS awareness of Adult females of slum areas in Agra.
3. To compare the AIDS awareness of Adult male and females of slum areas in Agra.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There exists, no significant difference between the AIDS awareness of Adult Male and Females of slum area in Agra.

Method of Study

Keeping the nature of the problem in the mind Descriptive Survey Method has been used for the collection of the data.

Selection of Sample

The simple random sampling method has been used by the researcher to collect the adult samples. It provides a more even spread of the units of the sample over the population. The researcher has selected 100 male and 100 female adults as shown in the following distribution:

Exhibiting total no. of Adults slum area wise

S. No.	Name of Slum area	Adults	
		Male	Female
1.	Nagla Boodhi	7	8
2.	Nagla Padi	8	7
3.	Jagdishpura	9	5
4.	Gyaspura	7	8
5.	Sevla	6	9
6.	Gopalpura	8	8
7.	Kalal Kheriya	5	6
8.	Kachpura	7	6
9.	Nagla Kazi Para	7	7
10.	Nagla Hevali	9	8
11.	Nare Mantola	6	7
12.	Nagla Chidda	8	6
13.	Gokulpura	6	8
14.	Teen Ka Nagla	7	7
TOTAL		100	100

Construction of AIDS Awareness Scale

The researcher has constructed a AIDS Awareness Scale for adults to measure AIDS awareness.

This scale has only 8 items and item has been exposed to two alternatives Yes, No and opinion.

Reliability of Tool

The reliability of the AIDS Awareness Scales was computed by Test retest method. Reliability of the "AIDS Awareness Scale" is 0.86.

Validity of Tool

Validity of a test provides a direct indication of the degree to which a test scores actually measures what they intended to measure. To ensure the content validity, the researcher tried make test items, direction and scoring procedures on the basis of theory procedure.

Statistical Techniques

Descriptive Statistics - Mean, Median, Mode, Percentage

Graphical Representation of Data

Finding of the Study**Finding Related to Objective-1**

On the basis of analysis of study results it is finding that only less than 40% male adults of slum areas in Agra have AIDS awareness. A large proportion of male adult's populations are unaware with AIDS/HIV. Adults want AIDS awareness knowledge to protect him, his family, society and country by dreadfulness of the disease.

Finding Related to Objective-2

On the basis of analysis of study results it is finding that only less than 35% female adults of slum areas in Agra have AIDS awareness. A large proportion of female adult's populations also are unaware with AIDS/HIV. Female is the mother of society. AIDS awareness knowledge is very necessary young female. Female adults also want AIDS awareness knowledge to protect him, her family by the disease.

Finding Related to Objective-3

The information was collected with the help of predesigned and pretested questionnaire. It was observed that the respondents belonged to 18 to 35 years, considered AIDS as a dangerous disease, still majority of them (78.0 percent) were unknown to full form of HIV. So far as mode of transmission was considered, less than one fifth respondents reiterated its transmission by infected blood, infected syringe (16.5 percent) and unprotected sex (34.0percent), while 27.5 percent

respondents said that all these modes are responsible for its spread. Though majority of the respondents were aware with the dreadfulness of the disease, still 28.0 percent of them did not consider AIDS as an end stage of HIV. As such this study reveals that a lot of efforts need to be done toward developing awareness among adults in slum areas of Agra.

Conclusion of the Study

The results of study reveals that majority of the respondents (63.5 percent) had no knowledge full form of HIV, while 36.5 percent respondents were familiar with Human Immune-deficiency Virus as the abbreviation of HIV. Three fifth respondents (58.5 percent) considered AIDS as a dangerous disease, while 41.5 percent of the respondents considered it as an infectious or a common disease. Further 16 percent of the respondents had knowledge of complications caused by this disease as the combination of signs like weight loss, severe fever with sweats, severe pneumonia and red brown pink blotches under skin or in mouth, followed by only weight loss (14.5 percent) and only severe fever with sweats (16.0 percent). Various modes of transmission reiterated by the respondents were blood transfusion from HIV infected person (22.0 percent); infected syringe (16.5 percent) and unprotected sex (34.0 percent). In addition only respondents (27.5 percent) opined that AIDS is transmitted through various modes like blood transfusion from HIV injected patient, unprotected sex and HIV infected syringe. 43.5 percent respondents also admitted that this disease can also be transmitted to the child from the infected mother, while 56.5 percent respondents were not aware of this mode of transmission.

Many complications are caused due to AIDS. 14.5 percent respondents of the present study, replied that tuberculosis is caused due to AIDS, followed by cancer and tumor both (20.0/20.0 percent) In addition 45.5 percent respondents reiterated for the presence of signs of meningitis and herpes simplex. Further three fourth respondents (72.0 percent) mentioned AIDS as last stage. Similarly (34.5 percent) respondents replied that they were aware with the serious consequences of the disease. This study reveals that still a lot of efforts need to be done toward developing awareness among adult (mainly for females) of slum areas of Agra.

Limitations of the Study

The present study is not an exception and researcher felt the following limitation in present investigation.

- The study will be delimited to adults of slum areas in Agra.

- The study will be delimited to adults of 18 to 35 Year age group.

Implications of the Study

- Research is of no value until their findings are applied for anything which may have some practical importance. Certain implication can also be derived from the findings of present investigation. These are as under.
 1. The investigation will help to make the adults to realize as important part of the society, to enable them to adjust in the social environment and to appreciate the entire process of growing up.
 2. The investigation will help in the construction of the curriculum frame work for AIDS awareness and sex-education. The preferences in the frame work will be based on the adult preferences.
 3. The investigation will help to adopt a format for developing AIDS awareness and sex-education.
 4. The investigation will help to indentify the existing subjects at different college stages, which will lend themselves to effective integration of the elements of AIDS awareness.

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